

Attitudinal Disposition of Teachers towards counsellors: Roles in Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State

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Abstract

The study focused on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers towards counsellors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State. Four research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. The design was considered appropriate since data were obtained from teachers in different schools that constituted the areas of study. The population of this study consisted of all secondary school teachers in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State. The sample for this study consisted of 160 teachers in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State. The researcher employed the purposive and random sampling techniques. The instruments used for the study was titled Teachers Attitude toward Counselors' Inventory (TATCI). The data collected were collated, coded and analyzed with the mean, descriptive statistic, the t-test statistics and the One Way ANOVA because of their appropriateness to the hypotheses. The finding revealed a slightly positive attitude of teachers' towards counsellors' roles in secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District of in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State, non-significant difference in hypotheses one and two and a significant difference in hypothesis three. Conclusion was drawn and recommendations made, which include among others that should organise workshops, conferences and seminars to sensitise teachers, students and parents on issues relating to counsellors' roles in schools. Ministry of Education should begin to incorporate counseling programmes into all schools, and categorically state their objectives in the school system.

Keywords: *Teachers attitude, Guidance, counseling, programme, counsellors' roles*

Introduction

Guidance and counselling (G&C) is an indispensable part of any school administration in all level of education. It has been identified as an important aspect in Educational Training institutions by many countries in the world, owing to its internationally recognized role of improving all aspects of education.

School counselling are student's advocates, often consulting with students regarding their future career path. Their main tasks usually involve advising students and addressing their academic readiness, as well as conducting individual and group counseling. The school counsellors make frequent assessments of students' performance and progress. They are in the school to support the academic achievement, career development, personal and social well-being of students, and make learning a positive experience.

School counselors serve as leaders and are perform a crucial role in the school curriculum. They help students to resolve, direct, or adopt with any development modifications regarding their self-image, value, self-assurance and peers family interaction (Kuhn, 2004). They provide guidance, support, and professional assistance and strive to improve student's decision making and edifices student's skills. Counselors also work with parents and administrators in order to assist in the improvement of the students' educational environment and learning outcome.

Teachers play a fundamental role in the social, moral and academic development of any society. The main responsibility of teachers and school staff is to provide students with quality academic education. According to Beesley (2005), teachers are the first and most effective assessors of counsellors. School counselors interact and collaborate consistently with teachers. This relationship plays an important role in the dynamics and the success of the counselors' work, especially since teachers are in the best position to assess a number of student outcomes and to refer them for counseling.

The function of school counselors has hugely changed since 1960. Before the 20th century, school counselors didn't exist. It was the teachers' responsibility to use a few minutes from their period to help students (Bawers & Hatch, 2002). Beginning with the industrial revolution in the 1900's, Schmidt (1999) stated that schools depended on teachers as being responsible to tackle the private, social, and vocational support to students. In the 1940's & 1950's a new form of school guidance was produced by E.G Williamson, which emphasized teaching skills (Kuhn, 2004). After the 1960's, professionals began identifying the role of the school counselor. Today, a school counselor identifies objectives and purposes, evaluates students' desires, and guides services within the school's curriculum.

The definition of the role of the school counselor and the tasks they actually engage in are continuously modified through the perceptions and expectations of parents, teachers, and administrators. In recent decades, school counselors have become an increasingly valued addition to school systems worldwide. In fact, a number of countries have passed laws that require their schools to be staffed with counselors (Amatea

& Clark, 2004). As such, gaining an understanding of the attitudinal dispositions, perceptions and expectations of teachers are necessary in understanding what counselors can offer and what can be expected of their work in the school, and how improvements can be made.

Attitudes are predispositions which have developed through long and complex process. Anasasi (1990) defined attitudinal dispositions as a tendency to react favourably or unfavourably towards a designated class of stimuli. According to Eiser (1986), attitudes are derived from individual evaluative beliefs summed together. Barker (2000) noted that attitudinal dispositions can be viewed as predictions toward behaviour. An individual attitudinal disposition about something is thought to affect behaviour, action and efficacy. For the purpose of this study, “teachers’ attitudinal dispositions are used to refer to how teachers conceive of the role and tasks of the counselor in relation to their own role and tasks, and to the expectations they have of the counselor.

A substantial number of researchers have studied teachers’ attitudinal dispositions toward school counsellors, most of which took place within Western societies, with a few emanating from Nigeria. Most researchers from the West have reported that teachers displayed positive attitudinal disposition toward school counsellors. For example, Cusky (1996) examined the perceptions of 152 teachers in public elementary schools and found that they viewed counselors to be most effective in consultation and support for teachers, and individual counseling for students. Amatea and Clark (2004) studied the perceptions of 23 teachers in elementary, middle, and high schools, concerning the importance of school counselors’ roles and found them to be positive. The results showed that teachers emphasized the need for counselors’ support for classroom instructions, and their importance in directing students with special needs to appropriate resources. In her survey of 188 teachers across the American Southwest, Beesley (2005), found that her participants were satisfied with the counselors’ roles in their schools. Similarly, Oyaziwo and Imonikhe (2002) examined how teachers viewed the job of school counselor at the secondary level and found positive perceptions all around.

On the contrary, a few studies revealed negative perceptions towards school counselors. For example, Stelzer (2003) surveyed 100 elementary teachers and found that only a few of them understood the job of the counselor and what counseling actually is. Moreover, Valine, Higgins, and Hatcher (1980) found that most teachers viewed counselors as ineffective. Previous studies by Achebe (1986), Bulus (2001), Adenula (1988), Denga (2001), Edet (2008) have shown that principals and teachers constitute the greatest obstacle to the success of guidance and counselors’ roles in schools. Ademola (1988) also attributed the negative attitudinal dispositions to the ignorance of principals and teachers about the relevance of guidance services in schools. Bulus (2001) believed that principals and teachers misconceive the counselors’ status, which create conflict between them. Denga (2001) stressed those principals who know little about counseling will not in any way appreciate the need for the counselors to be relieved of heavy teaching load and other co-curriculum duties. Achebe (1986) stated that some principals are rigid and traditional, and would not

welcome new ideas. Edet (2008) found that teachers' perceptions of vocational guidance in Calabar metropolis were significantly negative.

Today in Nigeria, most Principals often mandate school counselors to teach school subjects at the expense of Counseling. The controversy has negative consequences on students who are left as sheep without shepherd. Consequently, existing empirical research that can intimate us on the attitude of teachers towards the roles of counselors in Nigeria schools is very limited. An investigation of the attitudinal dispositions of teachers towards school counselors' roles has significant impetus for the fact that teachers and counselors need to establish their specific functions and respect each another. This study is timely and necessary because both stakeholders need to complement each other for the desired academic objectives to be achieved.

Statement of the problem

Counselors occupy a veritable position in any educational setting, and that is why the Federal Government of Nigeria reemphasized the need for guidance and counselors' roles in the national policy on education (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004). It is sad to state that the mindset of most teachers differ significantly towards counselors' roles in schools, and these have breed conflict of interest in our educational system. Most school heads allocate many subjects to the counselors to reach at the expense of their responsibilities. Counselors are often envied by some teachers for occupying lofty offices and roles. When school counselors are deprived from performing their roles effectively in schools the victims are the students and outright failure of the educational objectives. It is therefore imperative to determine the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in schools, with a view to correct any anomalies in their relationship. This will enable schools to ensure a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning, and achieve the anticipated educational objectives in our school system.

Purpose of the study

This study intended to:

1. Determine the level of attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counsellors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.
2. Determine whether difference exists among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counsellors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.
3. Investigate the difference between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counsellors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.
4. Establish the difference between rural and urban schools on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counsellors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

Research Questions

1. What is the attitudinal disposition of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?
2. Does difference exist among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?
3. Does difference exist between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?
4. What is the difference between rural and urban schools on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?

Method

The descriptive survey design was utilized for the study. The design was considered appropriate since data were obtained from teachers residing in different schools that constituted the areas of study. The population of this study consisted of all teachers in Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State. The sample of this study comprised of 170 teachers. The researcher employed the purposive and random sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used to select 4 Local Government Areas out of 9 that constituted Delta North Senatorial District of Delta, and seventeen secondary schools from the zone. Random sampling technique was used to select 10 teachers from each of chosen schools. The 4 Local Government Areas used for the study were:

Ukwuani Local Government Areas of Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State, Ndokwa West Local Government Areas of Delta North Senatorial District, State, Ndokwa East Local Government Areas of Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State and Ika South Local Government Areas of Delta North Senatorial District, State.

The instrument for data collection in the study was a questionnaire titled: "Teachers Attitude toward Counselors' Inventory" (TATCI). It consisted of two parts: section A and section B. Section A is concerned with the biographical data of respondents while section B is the question part, which is made up of 20 items. Section B is based on modified Likert- scale with 4 response categories: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options on the items was weighed on Likert format, with SA=4, A=3, D= 2, and SD=1. These scoring apply to positive (P) items and the reverse, however, were the cases with negative items. The maximum score was 80 while the least score was 20. The weighted mean of 2.50 ($4+3+2+1/4=2.50$) was used to evaluate the outcomes of the study.

The instrument is a 20 item questionnaire drawn by the researcher. The questionnaire was validated by five experts in the areas of Measurement and Evaluation, Psychology and Guidance and Counseling in the Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria, and Novena University Ogume. The corrected versions as suggested by the experts were used for the study.

A pilot study was administered to 30 teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State of Nigeria, outside the targeted areas of study. Test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and the data generated from the respondents was analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. A reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained, which was deemed adequate for the study.

The questionnaires were distributed to 170 teachers in 4 Local Government Areas of Delta North Senatorial District of Delta North Senatorial District of Delta State of Nigeria with the help of four research assistants. The completed questionnaires were retrieved through the same research assistants. However, 160 questionnaires were returned out of the original 165 distributed, which was about 95% success. Descriptive statistics and the mean, the t- test and One Way Analysis of Variance statistics because of their appropriateness in to the research questions.

Results

Research question 1: What is the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?

Table 1: Descriptive on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

S/N	QUESTIONS	N	Sum	Men	Std.D v	Decision
1	I cherish the role of counselors in the school.	160	548	3.43	0.87	Agreed
2	Teachers cannot perform the function of counselors in the school.	160	525	3.30	0.93	Agreed
3	School counselors should be exempted from teaching school subjects,	160	524	3.28	0.98	Agreed
4	I feel obligated to refer students to the school counselor.	160	500	3.31	0.93	Agreed
5	The school cannot function properly without the counselors.	160	296	1.85	0.89	Disagreed
6	I support separate budget for counseling activities in the school.	160	292	1.83	0.89	Disagreed
7	Treating students behaviour problems can better be referred to the school counselor.	160	408	2.55	1.2	Agreed
8	It is wrong for teachers to usurp the functions of school counselors.	160	416	2.60	0.89	Agreed
9	Administering psychological tests is the exclusive role of the school counselors.	160	424	2.65	1.07	Agreed
10	Vocational guidance is the exclusive role of the school counselors.	160	380	2.38	0.99	Disagreed

11	Counselors' worth in the schools is underestimated.	160	432	2.70	1.03	Agreed
12	I support the inclusion of counseling programmes in the school Time table.	160	408	2.55	0.89	Agreed
13	I usually consult the school counselor for professional advice.	160	400	2.50	0.95	Agreed
14	I do not envy the counselors' position in the school management cadre.	160	448	2.80	0.98	Agreed
15	I advocate a standard office for the school counselor.	160	244	1.53	0.67	Disagreed
16	I do not feel jealous when counselor is given much attention by school heads and parents.	160	408	2.55	1.2	Agreed
17	I often collaborate with school counselor to facilitate decision on students' welfare.	160	400	2.50	1.14	Agreed
18	Counseling activities in the school system are very reliable and should be supported.	160	368	2.30	1.1	Disagreed
19	I support separate budget for school Counseling programme.	160	220	1.38	0.56	Disagreed
20	School counselors usually influence the academic performance of students.	160	412	2.58	0.87	Agreed
	Total	3200	8053	2.53	0.96	Agreed

Table 1 revealed the descriptive statistics on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The analysis indicated a total sum of 8053, an average mean of 2. and standard deviation of .96. The average mean of 2.53 is higher than weighted mean of 2.5. The implication is that attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State is slightly positive.

Research question 2: Does difference exist among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?

Table 2: Descriptive on the difference between teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
NCE	44	42.91	9.19	1.39	40.11	45.70	28.00	63.00
Degree	96	51.50	8.17	.839	49.84	53.16	35.00	63.00
Post Degree	20	65.40	2.48	.559	64.23	66.56	63.00	70.00
Total	160	50.88	10.38	.829	49.25	52.49	28.00	70.00

Table 2 revealed descriptive on the difference between teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The table gives categories of the subjects into NCE, Degree and Post Degree holders. A total

of 160 teachers participated in the study. Out of this figure, 44 are NCE holders, 96 has degree while 20 are post graduates. The mean scores for NCE holders, degree and post graduates are 42.91, 51.50 and 65.40 respectively; with a total mean score of 50.88.

Table 4:
ANOVA statistic on the difference between teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7049.064	2	3524.532	54.81	.000
Within Groups	10096.436	157	64.31		
Total	17145.500	159			

At .05 level of significant.

The one-way statistics revealed a significant difference between and within groups as shown in table 6 above with $F(54.81 = df, 2/559, p = .000)$. Research question which sought to determine whether difference existed among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State was affirmed in the analysis. The implication from the study was that difference existed among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District; Delta State. In order to determine the actual differences between the three categories of academic qualifications involved in the study, a posteriori test was conducted. The Turkey HSD post hoc test in table 4 below revealed that teachers with degree certificates mean difference was higher (22.49) followed by those with NCE qualification (13.90) and lastly by those with Post qualification (8.59). All the mean differences were significant at $p = .000$. The finding from the study is that Degree teachers were more positively disposed towards school counselors, followed by the NCE certificates teachers while those with post graduates certificates manifested poorer attitude towards school counselors.

Post Hoc Tests

Table 4

Tukey HSD Multiple Comparisons on the difference between teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

(I) Qualification	(J) Qualification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
NCE	Degree	-8.59	1.45994	.000	-12.0454	-5.1365
	Post Degree	-22.49*	2.16263	.000	-27.6080	-17.3738
Degree	NCE	8.59	1.45994	.000	5.1365	12.0454
	Post Degree	-13.90*	1.97112	.000	-18.5640	-9.2360
Post Degree	NCE	22.49	2.16263	.000	17.3738	27.6080
	Degree	13.90	1.97112	.000	9.2360	18.5640

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Research question 3: Does difference exist between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?

Table 6: T-test statistics on the difference between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t	Sig.
Male	72	51.33	11.087	1.307	158	5.04	0.14
Female	88	50.50	9.820	1.05			

At .05 level of significant.

The result in Table 6 rejected research question 3 which sought to determine if difference existed between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State at $t(0.14, df=158, p > .05)$. The outcome showed that difference does not exist between male and females on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The implication is that there is no difference between male and female teachers on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State as shown in the proximity of their means (51.33 for male and 50.50 for female).

Research question 4: What is the difference between rural and urban schools teachers on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State?

Table 7

T-test Statistics on the difference between rural and urban schools teachers on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t	Sig.
Rural	96	51.83	10.97	1.12	158	1.43	.153
Urban	64	49.438	9.34	1.167			

At .05 level of significant.

The result in Table 7 depicted the difference between rural and urban schools teachers on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State, at $t(1.43)$, $df= 158$, $P<.05$. The implication was that difference does not exist between rural and urban teachers on the on their attitudinal dispositions towards counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State with close means of 51.83 and 49.44 for rural and urban teachers respectively.

Discussion

The study focused on teachers' attitudinal disposition towards counselors' roles in Schools in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The outcome of the study revealed that the attitudinal disposition of Teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State was moderate. This outcome is at variance with that of Achebe (1986), Bulus (2001), Adenula (1988), Denga (2001), Edet (2008) who found that teachers' perceptions of school counselors in Calabar metropolis were significantly negative. However, the findings of the study concurred with that of Beesley (2005) and Oyaziwo and Imonikhe (2002) who found that teachers were satisfied with the counseling services in their schools.

Research question 2 which sought to determine whether difference existed among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State affirmed that difference exist. This disagrees with the finding of Bulus (2001) who believed that principals and teachers misconceive the counselors' status, which create conflict between them. The outcome of the study is also at variance with the view of Denga (2001) who stressed the principal who knows little about counseling will not in any way appreciate the need for the counselor to be relieved of heavy teaching load and other co-curriculum duties. Achebe (1986) also stated that some principals are rigid and traditional, and would not welcome new ideas.

Research question 3 revealed that there is no difference between male and female teachers on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The finding agrees with Amatea and Clark (2004) whose study showed that teachers irrespective of gender emphasized the need for the counselors' support for classroom instructions, and their importance in directing students with special needs to appropriate resources.

Implications for Counselling

The outcome of the study would help school counselors be equipped with the information that would adequately make them adhere strictly with Counseling ethics in education. School counselors could organize individual and group counseling for teachers and other school staff to enlighten them on their roles within the school setting'. This no doubt would reduce the negative impression of teachers towards the counselors' role.

Conclusions

The study focused on teachers attitudinal dispositions towards counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The outcome of the study revealed that the attitude of teachers toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State is slightly positive. Difference existed among teachers with varying academic qualifications on the attitudinal dispositions toward counselors' roles in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District; Delta State. There is no difference between male and female and between rural and urban teachers on the attitudinal dispositions of teachers toward counselors' in secondary schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. However, There is the need for counselors to organise workshops and seminars to sensitise teachers and educate parents on the roles of school counselors.

Recommendations

1. There is the need for counselors to organise workshops and seminars to sensitise teachers and educate parents on the roles of school counselors.
2. Ministry of Education should begin a strategy to incorporate school counseling into all schools.
3. The Ministry of Education needs to state the objectives and procedures concerning the rules, applications and roles of the school counselors.

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